

Energy Modelling for alternative scenarios in Paraguay using OSeMOSYS.

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Energy modelling, OSeMOSYS, Paraguay, Hydroelectric power, Solar VP power, Onshore Wind power, Petroleum derivatives, Translating Policy into Modelling Assumptions (TPMA), Electrification of Transportation (ELEC).

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Executive Summary

Paraguay's energy sector, heavily reliant on hydropower (99.5% of installed capacity), exports surplus electricity to Brazil and Argentina. However, the transport sector's dependence on imported oil products (39% of national consumption) presents a challenge. This study aims to explore pathways for reducing emissions and oil imports by diversifying Paraguay's energy matrix and electrifying transport.

Analysis of various scenarios highlights the need for strategic energy diversification and technology investment. While the BAU scenario maintains the status quo, the TPMA and ELEC scenarios prioritize non-conventional renewables and electrification. Although these alternatives require higher investments, they offer long-term benefits, especially in emission reductions. The ELEC scenario demonstrates significant potential in lowering CO₂ emissions by 2030, emphasizing the importance of infrastructure development and foreign investment. Future research should focus on further analyzing the economic and environmental benefits of integrating wind and solar power, reducing hydropower reliance, and exploring additional technologies like hydrogen and biofuels to enhance Paraguay's energy sustainability.

1. Introduction

Paraguay presents a significant energy landscape for the Latin American region (IEA, 2023). Its energy matrix is primarily driven by renewable energy, specifically hydroelectric power, which accounts 99.5% of the country's installed capacity (IRENA, 2021). While the remaining small percentage of the energy matrix is supplied by small thermal generation plants (OLADE, 2024).

The country primarily relies on two binational hydroelectric plants that allow it to generate more electricity than it consumes. As a result, Paraguay shares electricity generation with Brazil through the Itaipú hydroelectric plant and with Argentina through the Yacyretá hydroelectric plant. Additionally, Paraguay has a third plant, Acaray, which is a national facility located on the Acaray River and is managed by the National Electricity Administration (ANDE) (ANDE, 2021).

National production is based on 40% hydroelectric power, 36% biomass, and 24% imported petroleum products. In terms of final energy consumption, biomass dominates with 43%, followed by fossil fuels with 40% and electricity 17%, primarily hydroelectric. Renewable energies such as wind and solar are minimally developed in Paraguay (Lucantonio, Sosa and Aiello, 2022).

The purpose of this modeling work is to evaluate Paraguay's energy system by identifying key areas for diversifying the energy mix and electrifying technologies that can reduce emissions and decrease oil imports to optimize national resources. The specific objectives are to analyze the current state of the energy system, model a diversification scenario and provide strategic recommendations based on the modeling results to guide public policies towards a more resilient and diversified energy system. These objectives are achieved by analyzing three scenarios including the Business-as-Usual (BAU), the Translating Policy into Modeling Assumptions (TPMA) scenario, and the Electrification of Transportation (ELEC) scenario.

2. Methodology

The open-source and free tool OSeMOSYS was used for the modeling. OSeMOSYS is an energy system optimization framework designed for long-term planning, as demonstrated in this study's 2050 projection. This exercise aligns with U4RIA objectives of community-centered, recoverability, reusability, repeatability, interoperability, and auditability. In the OSeMOSYS model, the electricity supply system is represented by import and extraction technologies, conversion technologies, power plants, transmission and distribution networks, and final energy demands for the various available fuels (Howells *et al.*, 2011).

The 'Starter Kit' energy system modeling data for Paraguay, available in the Zenodo repository (Cannone *et al.*, 2021), served as the foundation for this energy modeling

study. This country-specific dataset accelerated the analysis process. However, historical data for primary and secondary energy production, existing capacity, generation, imports, exports, energy sub-sector demands (residential, industrial, commercial, and transportation), and transmission and distribution loss factors were updated to ensure that the projections were based on calibrated information from the 2015-2022 period.

The data were sourced from publicly available information, including international reports, journal articles, public or private databases, and reports from key energy sector ministries and entities in Paraguay. To conduct the study, three scenarios were developed to evaluate the country's installed capacity, electricity generation from the energy mix, the associated costs, and the greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions released as carbon dioxide equivalent.

1. The baseline scenario (BAU) is designed to predict the future by maintaining the same behavior as the historical years, keeping the same percentage of hydroelectric generation to meet future demand, with no mitigation measures included.
2. The second scenario is Translating Policy into Modeling Assumptions (TPMA), where the focus is on non-conventional renewable energies. To achieve this, investments in hydroelectric power plants are limited in the 2030, allowing the model to introduce the technologies deemed most appropriate in terms of costs and emissions for the country. The scenario proposes a transition towards a more diversified energy matrix, with a greater emphasis on non-conventional renewable sources such as solar and wind power (IRENA, 2021).
3. The third scenario is Electrification of Transportation (ELEC), aimed at evaluating the reduction of imports and foreign dependence through the incorporation of electric technologies, following the country's Electric Mobility Master Plan (PMME) (MADES, 2023). The country aims to electrify 80% of the bus fleet and 75% of the private vehicle fleet by 2050 (CCSI, 2021).

Paraguay is driving a transition towards a more diversified and sustainable energy matrix, prioritizing renewable sources like solar and wind. This decision is based on the need to adapt to the growing climate risks affecting hydroelectric generation, such as variability in rainfall and extreme weather events. By diversifying its energy mix, Paraguay aims to ensure energy security, reduce its vulnerability to climate fluctuations, and promote sustainable development.

These scenarios are presented in Figure 1 and are selected to assess the country's ability to expand its energy mix and reduce reliance on a single energy source, primarily hydroelectric power.

Figure 1. Studied Scenarios for Paraguay's Energy Modeling.

This methodology allows for an evaluation of Paraguay's energy system, providing viable alternatives for the country in both diversifying the energy mix and incorporating electric technologies in transportation.

3. Results and Discussion

The study analyzes defined scenarios from 2020 to 2050, calibrated using data from 2015 to 2022. Figure 2 shows the installed capacity of energy plants required to meet electricity demand in the energy sub-sectors. During the first decade of the three scenarios, the current installed capacity is sufficient to satisfy demand, resulting in a constant pattern. However, by 2035, the country will need to adopt new technologies to meet growing demand.

The BAU scenario continues to prioritize hydroelectric plants, while the TPMA and ELEC scenarios introduce non-conventional renewable energy sources like solar and onshore wind power. However, these renewables are less efficient at meeting electricity demand compared to hydroelectric plants. As a result, the installed capacity required for these scenarios is higher.

In the BAU scenario, hydropower technology is the most dominating, reaching an installed capacity of about 18 GW by 2050. However, the two alternative scenarios have shown a shift to variable renewable sources such as solar and wind. If solar PV technologies deployment started early 2035 in the TPMA and ELEC scenarios, onshore wind becomes visible from 2040. The total installed capacity of solar PV is about 15 GW and 12 GW in TPMA and ELEC scenarios, respectively, in 2050. In addition, onshore capacity reaches 16 and 21 GW in the same year, in the TPMA and ELEC scenarios, respectively. However, the hydropower capacity remains constant at 10 GW for the two alternative scenarios.

The ELEC scenario shows a higher requirement for installed capacity compared to the TPMA scenario due to the country's effort to electrify transportation. It's important to highlight that to facilitate the integration of these non-conventional technologies, the model was constrained in the Total Annual Max Capacity Investment for hydroelectric power plants starting from 2030, with the aim to evaluate the potential of alternative non-conventional options that could be introduced in the country.

The model also incorporates some technologies with minimal proportions that exist within the country but are not feasible for expansion in the projections due to economic factors or limited capacity, as a result, these technologies do not show any growth percentage. A potential research avenue could explore the electrification of transportation without imposing restrictions on hydroelectric investments to analyze the associated cost implications of a potential fourth scenario.

Figure 2. Installed capacity (GW) in the country for the 3 study scenarios.

Figure 3 illustrates the increasing demand for electricity generation throughout the study period. The country possesses abundant solar and wind resources, but, until recently, hydroelectric plants have been sufficient to meet demand. However, with the growing need for electricity to power transportation, non-conventional technologies, such as solar and onshore wind, are becoming necessary. In the third scenario, these technologies are estimated to contribute approximately 50 PJ to meet the additional electricity requirements.

Drawing from the Decarbonization Pathways for Paraguay's Energy Sector (CCSI et al., 2021), the study estimates the percentage of transportation electrification. Paraguay has set ambitious targets: 75% of private vehicles and 80% of public buses should be electric by 2050. Due to limited data on motorcycles, the same electrification rate as private vehicles is assumed. While hybrid vehicles, hydrogen technologies, and biofuels were

not analyzed in this study due to time constraints, they could be promising areas for future research and updates on Paraguay's energy sector.

Figure 3. Electricity generation (PJ) from the projected technologies.

Figure 4. Transport demand (Gpkm) assessment for the inclusion of electric technologies.

Figure 4 illustrates a shift in transportation demands, with electric technologies gaining prominence over combustion technologies. Buses require the most energy, while private cars have a relatively smaller energy demand. Given this, Paraguay should assess its current public transportation system and continue investing in this sector to alleviate traffic congestion in major cities like Asunción (Rivarola, 2020).

Both scenarios demonstrate increased total costs compared to the baseline scenario. This is anticipated, given the proposed investments in new electricity generation

technologies and transportation electrification. Figure 5 reveals an additional cost of 2,000 MUSD for solar and onshore wind power, while transportation electrification requires an investment of over 3,100 MUSD. Despite the technical justifications for diversifying the energy matrix and electrifying transportation, these costs may not fully justify the proposed investments.

To assess the investment required for each scenario relative to the BAU, the percentage of investment needed compared to the most recent GDP (USD 42.96 billion in 2023) was calculated. The TPMA scenario demands 5% of the GDP, while the ELEC scenario requires a significant 12%. Given Paraguay's economic capacity, both percentages are considered high, suggesting that foreign investment might be necessary to implement these scenarios.

Alternative approaches could be explored to reduce the required investments. For example, limiting hydropower investment could be gradually phased in over time instead of starting abruptly in 2030. The third scenario requires higher capital investment costs due to the need to import electric vehicles and invest in related infrastructure. However, it also offers lower variable costs compared to the other scenarios, likely because electric vehicles have lower maintenance requirements. It's important to note that transportation electrification can reduce petroleum derivative imports, a factor not explicitly modeled in this study but a potential area for future research. This could create a more favorable cost-benefit scenario for Paraguay.

Figure 5. Total costs (MUSD) per scenario as a percentage of the country's 2023 GDP.

As expected, the first two scenarios follow a similar emissions trajectory. This is because both scenarios replace hydroelectric plants with renewable solar and onshore wind power, which are assumed to have zero emissions. The projected emissions mainly stem

from imported petroleum derivatives used in the transportation sector and biomass energy generation, primarily for industrial purposes.

The third scenario demonstrates lower emissions due to the transition from petroleum-based transportation to electric vehicles. This shift starts in 2030 and is expected to reduce emissions by less than 8,600 kt CO₂ by 2050, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Projected GHG emissions (kt CO₂) for each scenario.

4. Conclusions, Policy insights, & Future Work

Conclusions

- Paraguay has the potential to diversify its energy matrix by incorporating wind and solar power plants.
- The ELEC scenario, while more costly, promotes emission reductions.
- Paraguay's current installed capacity can meet electricity demand until around 2035. After that, the country will need to adopt new technologies to keep up with increasing energy needs.
- The TPMA and ELEC scenarios, which prioritize non-conventional renewable energy sources, require more installed capacity than the BAU scenario.
- While all alternative scenarios involve higher total costs due to technology investments, the ELEC scenario offers a significant reduction in CO₂ emissions starting in 2030.

Policy insights

- Prioritize the construction of wind or solar power plants over new hydroelectric plants to diversify the energy matrix.

- Invest in electric charging infrastructure to incentivize the transition to electric transportation.

Future Work

- Analyze the economic and environmental benefits of wind and solar power plants compared to hydroelectric plants and consider reducing reliance on hydropower.
- Evaluate the economic advantages of transportation electrification by reducing petroleum derivative imports.
- Explore transportation electrification without limiting hydropower, and investigate hybrid, hydrogen, and biofuel technologies for future research.
- Prioritize the integration of electric technologies in transportation to enhance sustainability and reduce emissions.
- Evaluate the economic benefits of reducing petroleum derivative imports due to transportation electrification.

5. References

- ANDE (2021) *Plan Maestro de Generación 2021-2040*. Available at: https://www.ande.gov.py/plan_maestro.php (Accessed: 21 August 2024).
- Cannone, C. *et al.* (2021) 'Selected "Starter Kit" energy system modelling data for Paraguay (#CCG)'. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-895567/v1>.
- CCSI (2021) *Paraguay's Energy Sector: Hydropower, Decarbonization, and Sustainable Development | Columbia Center on Sustainable Investment*. Available at: <https://ccsi.columbia.edu/content/paraguays-energy-sector-hydropower-decarbonization-and-sustainable-development> (Accessed: 20 August 2024).
- Howells, M. *et al.* (2011) 'OSeMOSYS: The Open Source Energy Modeling System: An introduction to its ethos, structure and development', *Energy Policy*, 39(10), pp. 5850–5870. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2011.06.033>.
- IEA (2023) *Latin America Energy Outlook 2023*, IEA. Available at: <https://www.iea.org/reports/latin-america-energy-outlook-2023> (Accessed: 20 August 2024).
- IRENA (2021) *Renewable Readiness Assessment Paraguay*. Available at: <https://www.irena.org/Energy-Transition/Country-engagement/RRA> (Accessed: 20 August 2024).
- Lucantonio, F., Sosa, J. and Aiello, R.G. (2022) 'Breve reseña del sector de energía en Paraguay', *IDB Publications* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.18235/0004321>.
- OLADE (2024) *SIEParaguay*. Available at: <https://sieparaguay.olade.org/default.aspx> (Accessed: 21 August 2024).

